

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF THE DERIVATIVE IN ECONOMIC PROBLEMS

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Abstract

The application of differential calculus in economics (limit analysis) allowed to reflect mathematically not only the state of economic objects, but also processes.

Keywords: limit analysis, derivative, the elasticity of supply and demand.

Introduction

In economics, average values are widely used: average costs per unit of production, average labour productivity, average cost of production, etc. This is an important tool for economic analysis, but when planning production changes, for example, its expansion, we face the following tasks: we need to assess how the result will change if the factor that affects it changes. For example, how costs will change when the volume of output or profit will change when the quantity of goods. Average values will not answer such questions. In problems of this type, you need to find the limit of the ratio of the increase in the effect to the increase in the factor, provided that the factor increase tends to zero, which is what causes the effect, or, as they say, the marginal effect. Thus, marginal values characterized not the state (as an average value), but the process of change of an economic object. The derivative is the rate of change of an economic object in time or by a certain factor.

It should be noted that the economy does not always allow the use of limit values due to the indivisibility of many economic calculations and the discreteness of economic indicators in time (monthly, quarterly, annual, etc.). At the same time, in some cases, we can move away from the discreteness of indicators and effectively use marginal values.

For example, using regression analysis we can, on the basis of discrete statistical data, find a functional relationship (continuous) between economic variables and apply a marginal analysis to the latter.

Economic value of the derivative

The economic meaning of a derivative is as follows: a derivative is the rate of change of some economic process over time or in relation to another factor under study. Labour productivity is the time derivative of output, and the derivative is equal to $\frac{\Delta C}{\Delta x}$, which expresses the marginal cost of production and characterizes the additional costs of producing a unit of additional output.

Marginal costs depend on the level of production (quantity of output) and are determined not by fixed

production costs, but only by variable costs (raw materials, fuel, etc.). Similarly, marginal revenue, marginal income, marginal product, marginal utility and other marginal values can be defined.

Marginal values characterize not a state (as a total or average value), but a process, a change in an economic object. Thus, the derivative acts as a rate of change of a certain economic object (process) in time or relative to another factor under study. It should be noted, however, that the economy does not always allow the use of marginal values due to the indivisibility of many objects of economic calculations and the discreteness of economic indicators in time (for example, annual, quarterly, monthly, etc.). At the same time, in some cases, it is possible to divert attention from the discreteness of indicators and effectively use threshold values.

The concept of elasticity of a function is often used to study economic processes and solve other applied problems.

Production costs C of a homogeneous product will be considered as a function of the quantity of products x produced, i.e. $C = C(x)$.

Suppose that the quantity of output increases by Δx . Products $x + \Delta x$ correspond to the production costs $C(x + \Delta x)$. Thus, the increase in the quantity of products Δx corresponds to an increase in production costs

$$\Delta C = C(x + \Delta x) - C(x)$$

The average increase in production costs per unit of output is equal to $\frac{\Delta C}{\Delta x}$.

The limit

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{C(x + \Delta x) - C(x)}{\Delta x} = C'$$

is called marginal cost of production and characterizes the additional costs of producing a unit of additional output.

In marginal analysis, an important concept is the marginal value (marginal value), which shows the value of an additional unit of production unit of output. If the cost function of an enterprise defines costs in hryvnias (this function is often also called a cost func-

tion), then marginal cost is defined as a function of marginal cost. In economic theory, it is commonly referred to as

$$C'(x) = MC.$$

Example 1. For the production cost function x units of production (in UAH) of the form

$$C(x) = 20x^2 - 0.5x^3.$$

Find the marginal cost if the production volume is 10 units per 20 units of output.

For to find the marginal cost, we need to find the derivative of the cost function, i.e.

$$C'(x) = (20x^2 - 0.5x^3)' = 40x - 1.5x^2$$

For $x = 10$ we have $C'(5) = 40 \times 10 - 1.5 \times 100 = 250$

For $x = 20$ we have $C'(20) = 40 \times 20 - 1.5 \times 400 = 200$

This means that with a production volume of 10 units, the cost of manufacturing the next (11) unit will be 250 UAH, and the cost of producing 21 units will be only 200 UAH.

Similarly, if we denote by $R(x)$ and $P(x)$ revenue from sales and profit (the difference between income and expenses) x units of products, then the limits

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta R(x)}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{R(x + \Delta x) - R(x)}{\Delta x} = R'(x)$$

$$= MR,$$

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta P(x)}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(x + \Delta x) - P(x)}{\Delta x} = P'(x)$$

are called marginal (marginal) income and marginal (marginal) profit, respectively.

The method of marginal analysis is particularly widely used in microeconomic theory, where economic laws are often formulated in terms of marginal values. Marginal values in the economy include: marginal cost, marginal income, marginal utility, marginal productivity, marginal propensity to consumption, etc.

Application of coefficients of elasticity in economic calculus

Consider the supply's function of the price of a certain type of product $q = x(p)$, where q – supply, p – price. It is often necessary to have a measure of the “sensitivity” of supply to price. It is often necessary to have a measure of the “sensitivity of supply to price changes. We can to use the derivative of the supply function, which by definition is equal to the frontier the ratio of the change in quantity supply to the change price:

$$\lim_{\Delta p \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta p} = x'(p).$$

This is undoubtedly a measure of sensitivity, but the problem is that this measure supply on the units of price and quantity supply. We can to consider a measure of supply sensitivity, which does not depend on the units of measurement. Economists have chosen the following as a measure of the sensitivity of supply to price changes is elasticity. Thus, the elasticity of price is defined as the percentage change in the quantity demanded divided by the percentage change in price.

So, the change in percentage increases (comparative increases) makes the concept of elasticity independent of units of measurement.

Elasticity in economics refers to the measure of how much the quantity demanded or supplied of a good or service responds to changes in factors such as price, income, or the price of other goods. It is a crucial concept in understanding market dynamics and consumer behavior. Elasticity helps economists and businesses predict how changes in market conditions can impact supply, demand, and pricing.

There are several types of elasticity in economics, the most commonly discussed being:

Price Elasticity of Demand (PED)

This measures how the quantity demanded of a good or service changes in response to a change in its price. It is defined as the percentage change in quantity demanded divided by the percentage change in price.

$$PED = \frac{\% \text{ change in quantity demanded}}{\% \text{ change in price}}$$

Elastic Demand: If the demand for a good is highly responsive to price changes ($PED > 1$), it is considered elastic. For example, luxury goods or non-essential items often have elastic demand.

Inelastic Demand: If the demand for a good is less responsive to price changes ($PED < 1$), it is considered inelastic. Basic necessities like food, medicine, or fuel tend to have inelastic demand.

Unitary Elastic Demand: If the percentage change in quantity demanded is exactly proportional to the percentage change in price ($PED = 1$), demand is said to be unitary elastic.

Price Elasticity of Supply (PES)

Price elasticity of supply measures how the quantity supplied of a good or service changes in response to a change in its price. It is calculated similarly to PED, but it applies to the supply side of the market.

$$PES = \frac{\% \text{ change in quantity supplied}}{\% \text{ change in price } P}$$

Elastic Supply: If the supply of a good is highly responsive to price changes ($PES > 1$), supply is considered elastic. This often happens in markets with flexible production processes or goods that can be easily produced.

Inelastic Supply: If the supply of a good is less responsive to price changes ($PES < 1$), supply is inelastic. This can occur in markets where production is difficult to increase quickly, such as in agriculture or for unique items.

Income Elasticity of Demand (YED)

Income elasticity of demand measures how the quantity demanded of a good changes in response to changes in consumer income. It helps classify goods as normal or inferior.

$$YED = \frac{\% \text{ change in quantity demanded}}{\% \text{ change in income}}$$

Positive YED: If the value is positive ($YED > 0$), the good is considered a normal good, meaning demand increases as income rises (e.g., luxury cars, high-end electronics).

Negative YED: If the value is negative ($YED < 0$), the good is considered an inferior good, meaning demand decreases as income rises (e.g., cheaper, lower-quality goods).

Cross-Price Elasticity of Demand (XED)

This measures how the quantity demanded of one good changes in response to a price change of another good. This concept is useful for understanding the relationship between substitutes and complements.

$$XED = \frac{\% \text{ change in quantity demanded of Good A}}{\% \text{ change in price of Good B}}$$

Substitutes: If the goods are substitutes (e.g., tea and coffee), XED will be positive, meaning that an increase in the price of one good will increase the demand for the other.

Complements: If the goods are complements (e.g., printers and ink cartridges), XED will be negative, meaning that an increase in the price of one good will decrease the demand for the other.

Pricing Strategy: Businesses use elasticity to determine optimal pricing strategies. For instance, if demand is elastic, lowering prices can lead to higher total revenue, whereas if demand is inelastic, increasing prices can lead to higher total revenue.

Taxation Policy: Governments use elasticity to assess the impact of taxes on goods. Taxes on inelastic goods (such as tobacco or alcohol) tend to generate stable revenue, while taxes on elastic goods can reduce consumption significantly.

Market Competition: Elasticity provides insights into how sensitive consumers are to price changes,

helping firms understand competitive dynamics. Products with more elastic demand may face more competition, while those with inelastic demand may have more pricing power.

Welfare Analysis: Elasticity is also used to study the welfare effects of price changes, helping economists understand how consumers and producers are affected by shifts in prices.

Elasticity is a fundamental concept that helps explain how different factors influence supply and demand in markets. Understanding elasticity allows businesses, policymakers, and economists to make informed decisions regarding pricing, taxation, and market interventions. Whether considering the impact of a price change, consumer income change, or the relationship between products, elasticity provides key insights into how markets function.

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